

A New Moth species in Europe: *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859 on the Island of Crete (Lepidoptera, Crambidae)

Imre Fazekas & Henry Edmunds

Abstract. *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859 was reported from the island of Crete and constitutes a new species in the European fauna. We present a description of the morphology of the species, along with diagrams of its sexual organs. The taxonomic status of members of the genus *Noorda* are briefly discussed. Molecular analysis suggests that the Cretan specimen has close affinities with examples from Israel and that these are significantly different to examples from elsewhere. The Cretan moth probably represents a separate (new) species, but further study is required to confirm this.

Key words. first record, Crete, *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859, similar species, distribution.

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Introduction

The second author operated a Robinson 125w mv moth trap in the garden of his house on the island of Crete (Villa Xylia, Agios Georgios). On May 2, 2024, a specimen of *Noorda blitealis* was caught in the trap. Specimens of unusual species from this trap are routinely shown to Colin W Plant, in England; he agreed with the identification.

Based on our knowledge of the literature, this is the first recorded occurrence of this species in Europe. It has a disjunct distribution world-wide. It is present throughout much of the Indian continent where it is known as a pest of *Moringa* (drumstick tree, horseradish tree, or malunggay). It also affects south-eastern Arabia, Israel, southern Africa, north-western Africa and has outlying populations in south-east Asia and northern Australia.

Moringa oleifera Lam. (Moringaceae) is one of the most widely consumed vegetables in Southeast Asia and West Africa. Throughout its distribution, it is subject to infestation by the leaf larva, *Noorda blitealis*. The latter is considered the most significant insect pest due to its year-round presence and the substantial damage it inflicts on moringa. *Noorda blitealis* is a larva in the destructive stage of the moringa tree's life cycle. Owing to the considerable expansion of moringa cultivation globally, the pest has continuously extended its geographical distribution in recent years. It is documented as a pest of moringa in Asia, its origin region, and several other tropical regions (Thumar et al. 2017).

Moringa oleifera originated in the Himalayan foothills. It has naturalised in numerous African countries, Caribbean islands, and Central America. Due to its low water requirements, it is particularly well-suited to arid regions, as it can be cultivated using rainwater without necessitating costly irrigation techniques. Its tuberous root enables it to survive without water for extended periods.

Moringa oleifera is a significant crop in Pakistan, India, Ethiopia, the Philippines, and Sudan. This species grows from sea level to an altitude of 600m, although it can be found up to 1000m in the Himalayas. It thrives in areas with annual rainfall of approximately 1000–2000mm. However, it exhibits drought tolerance and can survive in regions with rainfall as low as 400mm (see. <https://www.gbif.org/pt/species/3054181>). It can establish itself in various geo-

Fig. 1. A *Moringa oleifera* from Nepal (Photo Krish Dulal)
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Moringa_oleifera_pods_NP.JPG

graphical areas where it is introduced, and greenhouse specimens exist. These factors contribute to the potential for further dissemination and proliferation of *Noorda blitealis*.

The Crete trap also contained specimens of several migratory species including *Hyles euphorbiae* (Linnaeus, 1758) (1 ex), *Hyles livornica* (Esper, 1758) [5 ex], *Utethesia pulchella* (Linnaeus, 1758) [1 ex], *Condica viscosa* (Freyer, 1831) [5ex], *Agrotis ipisilon* (Hufnagel, 1766)[1 ex], *Heliothis peltigera* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) [2 ex] and *Grammodes stolidata* (Fabricius, 1775) [1 ex]. *Condica viscosa* is a species that occurs from the Canaries across northern parts of Africa to Arabia and Asia Minor, Israel, Iran etc.). Understanding the potential geographical source of the Cretan example requires a consideration of the taxonomic status of the species.

Taxonomic position

Noorda Walker, 1859 is the only genus in the subfamily Noordinae Minet, 1980 (1 genus, 17 species). According to Regier et al. (2012), the Noordinae comprise 16 Old World tropical species, although some of these species have been incorrectly placed in Noordinae.

The synapomorphies of Noordinae include unusual tympanal organs that are partially embedded in the thorax and have a reduced, unilobed, and bladeliike praecinctorium, as well as male genitalia characterised by broadly rounded valvae, a long and slender uncus, and gnathos with a concise median element (Minet, 1980). Minet assigned secondary importance to the apomorphic traits that *Noorda* shares with other groups, particularly the squaliform structures attached to the vinculum found in Odontiinae and Schoenobiinae. The molecular tree, on which *Noorda* is well separated from both Odontiinae and (especially) Schoenobiinae, supports the in-

terpretation that this similarity reflects homoplasy and suggests that the definition of squaliform structures in these three clades should be re-evaluated.

According to Amsel (1965), two species of *Noorda blitealis* are known from the eremic sub-region of the Palearctic, namely *Noorda blitealis* Wlk. from Jordan Valley, Beirut, and SE Iran (Baluchistan and Fars), and *Epinoorda caradjae* Rbl. from the Jordan Valley and S Iran (Fars). In addition, Zerny described *Noorda atripalpalis* from Kordofan in 1917.

Processing of Abyssinian Microlepidoptera from the yield W. Richter (Stuttgart) also revealed the presence of the *blitealis* in Abyssinia. However, doubts arose regarding the classification of these specimens as *N. blitealis* owing to the presence of three large metallic abdominal spots, whereas specimens from Palearctic regions had five or six corresponding spots. As a result, the following question arises: What is true *blitealis*? At the 12th International Entomological Congress in London in 1964, it was established based on the poorly preserved female holotype of *blitealis* from Ceylon (sp. 20 mm) that *blitealis* is the species possessing five abdominal metal spots in the female; hence, the species reported from the eremic subregion of the Palearctic belong to this species, while the Abyssinian specimens are not assigned to *blitealis* but to an as-yet undescribed species that needs to be diagnosed.

***Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859**

= *Argyria holocrossa* Meyrick, 1902

= *Scopula subjectalis* (Walker, 1866)

= *Noorda moringae* Tams, 1938

Male individuals typically measure between 19 and 21 mm in length, whereas females are generally 22 to 24 mm in length. On average, this species exhibits smaller dimensions and less robust morphology compared to *trimaculalis*. The shiny metallic lines and spots in this species are golden bluish in hue, rather than intense bluish, as in *trimaculalis*. The palps are also shiny metallic, but less golden in colour compared to the *trimaculalis*. The abdomen featured six large black spots on each side from the third to the eighth (seventh) segment, with five spots in the sixth segment. These spots exhibit intense bluish shimmering and metallic scales towards the back, with the bluish scales being most strongly developed on the third segment and decreasing in number towards the end of the abdomen. The upper surface of the abdomen is brownish-yellowish and lacks or has only a few metallic scales.

New observation. 1 male, Crete, Villa Xylia, Agios Georgios 74056, 02.05.2024. leg. et coll. H. Edmunds

Fig. 2. *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859, adult: male, Crete, Villa Xylia, Agios Georgios 74056, 02.05.2024

Figs 3–4.
The potential habitat of *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859 on the island of Crete

A leg from this Cretan specimen was detached by Colin Plant and conveyed via David Lees at the Natural History Museum (London) to NAME OF LABORATORY Jordan Beasley for sequencing of the CO1 gene of the mDNA. The results are presented in Fig. 5.

Results of sequencing of the CO1 gene of the mitochondrial DNA of the Cretan *Noorda* specimen.

>Noorda_ABV2008 0.61pc distant C9N05RA7_F06

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AACATTATATTTTATTTTGGGAATTTGAGCAGGAATAGTAGGAACATCTTTAAGTT-
TATTAATTCGAGCTGAATTAGGAAACCCAGGATCTCTAATTGGAGATGATCAAATT
TATAATACTATTGTTACAGCTCACGCTTTTATTATAATTTTCTTCATAGTAATACCTA
TTATAATTGGGGGATTTGGTAATTGATTAGTTCCATTAATATTAGGAGCTCCTGATA
TAGCCTTTCCCCG
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This sequence places the sample in BIN BOLD: ABV2008, indicating that it is closely related to Israeli specimens rather than to typical *blitealis*. This relationship is expressed in the BOLD joining tree in Fig. 5.

It seems highly probable on the basis of these data, that the Cretan specimens were of Israeli origin. The DNA results also strongly indicate that this population represents a new and separate species, though describing it on the basis of a single, probable migrant specimen is unwise. A broader review of the genus is called for.

Fig. 5. Explanation in the text

Fig. 6. The tentative spatial distribution of *Noorda blitealis* Walker, 1859 is depicted as follows: a black arrow designates the island of Crete, marking the initial European sighting. Black circles represent frequently documented locations, whilst black dots provide a schematic illustration of sporadic observations.

Similar species.

Noorda maledivica Fischer, 2018

According to Fischer (2018), *N. blitealis* and *N. maledivica* can be distinguished by: The *Noorda maledivica* has an almost constant and significantly smaller forewing span. The forewings appeared narrower in *N. maledivica* than those in *N. blitealis*.

Figs 7-8. 7. *Noorda maledivica* Fischer, 2018 adult,

(© https://v3.boldsystems.org/index.php/Taxbrowser_Taxonpage?taxid=890302)

8. *Noorda blitealis* specimen from Nigeria, this species is very variables, especially in the pattern of the forewings (compare with Figure 2, the specimen from the island of Crete)

Figs 9-11. Male genitalia of *Noorda* spp.

- 9.** *N. blitealis*, Iran.
10. *N. trimaculalis*, Etiopia.
11. *N. caradjae*, Palestina.
 (After Amsel 1965)

Noorda caradjae (Rebel, 1902)

Significantly smaller than *blitealis* and *trimaculalis* and immediately distinguishable from both by completely uncoloured, slightly but not metallically shining, chamois-coloured palps, the last limb of which is also much less beak-shaped and more truncated. Forewings with only one premarginal transverse line, whose scales have a bluish metallic lustre, similar to the *blitealis*.

Noorda trimaculalis Amsel, 1965

The species is not only very close to *N. blitealis*, but also has the same tendency towards variability. In both cases, the centre of the forewings can be lightened or equally darkened. In general, dark scales were more intense in *N. trimaculalis*. The labial palpi is slender and beak-shaped. The first limb is chamois-coloured, and the other two limbs are dark brown. The ends of the 2nd and third limbs have an intense metallic lustre (reddish, purple, violet), similar to the maxillary palpus. In *A. blitealis*, the palps are shiny silver-golden and less intensely shiny overall. There were no differences in the antennae.

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Internet resources

- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9506611/>
- <https://www.gbif.org/search?q=Noorda%20blitealis> (28.05.2024)
- https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?dataset_key=50c9509d-22c7-4a22-a47d-8c48425ef4a7&taxon_key=1888346
- <http://lepidoptera.butterflyhouse.com.au/noor/blitealis.html> (28.05.2024)
- <https://inaturalist.ca/taxa/503435-Noorda>
- [https://v3.boldsystems.org/index.php/Public_SearchTerms?query=Noorda\[tax\]](https://v3.boldsystems.org/index.php/Public_SearchTerms?query=Noorda[tax])
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